

INNOVATIVE USES OF NEXT GENERATION OF CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Recently, novel heat-directed carbon/carbon composites have been developed by our group in JAXA and KIT. The heat-directed carbon/carbon composites are controlled-multifunctional composites which contain spatial variations in both of reinforcements and matrix for the specific purpose of controlling the heat transfer by conduction on the in-plane direction of the hot structures. Based on the success of the basic experimental and numerical research on heat-directed carbon/carbon composites, several innovative uses can be introduced for next generation of advanced composite materials, for examples: improving heat transfer efficiency for smarter and smaller heat exchangers, saving energy and environment, reducing thermal stresses of thin hot structures, using as semi passive or active thermal protection systems without need of working fluids or convective cooling systems for re-entry space vehicles, and having higher Seebeck effect, direct conversion from temperature difference along the composites to electricity.

Keywords: Controlled-multifunctional, Carbon/carbon, Heat-directed, Hybrid, Nanocomposites, Innovative uses

INTRODUCTION

Recently, increasing demands for smarter and smaller products calls for the development of multiphase and multifunctional composites. These materials are used not only as structural materials but also satisfy the needs for additional functionalities such as thermal, electrical, magnetic, optical, chemical, biological, etc [1]. Furthermore, the authors of this research strongly believe the future of composite materials will not only have purely multifunctional properties, but they will have controlled-multifunctional properties. Therefore in this research, novel controlled-multifunctional carbon/carbon composites, called heat-directed carbon/carbon composites, were designed, fabricated and examined experimentally and numerically as well as some innovative uses were discussed.

Heat-Directed Composite Materials

The heat-directed composites materials have unique property which can conduct the majority of the transferred heat by conduction to the preferred area or certain direction of the thermal structure as shown in Figure 1. This unique heat-directed property can be attained by varying the in-plane thermal conductivity of the composites functionally.

Fig. 1: (a) Heat exchanger, (b) Concept of heat transfer in traditional materials; and (c) Concept of heat transfer in the suggested heat-directed materials

Fig. 2: Full-field Infrared observations of temperature distribution of (a) heat-directed carbon/carbon composites using functionally dispersed carbon nanotubes through the matrix (b) heat-directed carbon/carbon composites using hybrid Pitch/PAN carbon fibers.

Materials

Two novel techniques were adopted to fabricate composite materials with heat-directed property. In the first technique, changing the in-plane thermal conductivity of the composites materials functionally was achieved by dispersing highly heat-conductive materials such as carbon nanotubes/nanofibers functionally throughout the carbon matrix of plain woven carbon fiber-reinforced carbon matrix composites, carbon/carbon composites [2]. While in the second technique, changing the in-plane thermal conductivity of the material functionally was achieved by using hybrid carbon fibers (Pitch-based and PAN-based carbon fibers with thermal conductivity of 320 and 6.3 W/m.k, respectively) in the same prepreg of the carbon/carbon composites [3].

Experimental Procedure

The fabricated heat-directed carbon/carbon composites have been examined experimentally and numerically. The in-situ full-field measurements using infrared, IR, system and the finite element simulation of the composites showed that the heat transfer direction can be substantially controlled either by just functionally dispersed a few percent of carbon nanotubes through the matrix of traditional long carbon fiber-reinforced carbon matrix composites as shown in Figure 2-a or by using hybrid PAN/Pitch based carbon fibers as reinforcements for the carbon/carbon composites as shown in Figure 2-b.

Potentially Innovative Uses of Heat-Directed Carbon/Carbon Composites

Based of the success of the basic experimental and numerical research on the heat-directed carbon/carbon composites, several innovative uses can be introduced for next generation of advanced composite materials, for examples: improving heat transfer efficiency for smarter and smaller heat exchangers, saving energy and environment, reducing thermal stresses of thin hot structures, using as semi passive or active thermal protection systems without need of working fluids or convective cooling systems for re-entry space vehicles, and having higher Seebeck effect, direct conversion from temperature difference along the composites to electricity.